

Samanyabhinay: In The Context Of Shringar Rasa In Kathak

Smt. Rohini Tushar Kulkarni¹, Dr. Vibha Dadeech²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Kathak, F.A.C.I.S, Sri Sri University ²Professor, Sri Sri Centre for Advanced Research in Kathak (SSCARK), Sri Sri University

Abstract:

Bharat first used the word Abhinaya in the 17th part of the first chapter of Natyashastra. Before considering other aspects of acting, it is necessary to try to understand its general form and departments according to the dramatic classical tradition. Bharat has described abhinaya as derived from Yajurveda.

**जग्राह पाठ्यमृगवेदात् सामभ्यो गीतमेव च
यजुर्वेदादभिनयान रसानाथखण्डादपि (ना.शा.1/17)¹**

It is from this fact that we get the indications of the concept of acting in the Sanskrit Dramatic tradition. In the eighth chapter of Natya Shastra, in India, it is mentioned that ‘ The act which , combined with its shakha, ang, upang , opens up numerous theatrical purposes and takes the drama towards its main purpose, is called abhinay.’ (Na. Sha.8/6-7)²

It is also clarified that acting is not direct intimation. It is called Bhavanukirtan. The etymological meaning of Anukirtan is ‘to say’, that is, while narrating any incident, there is always scope for change in it to maintain curiosity and entertainment, that is, Anukirtan also means feeling. That is, to say the main sensitive parts and the essential elements of that incident. Acting is a performing art which, despite being related to reality, is one level above reality.³

¹ Dr, Agrawal Archana, Natya Shastriya Abhinay Siddhant avam Prayog, publisher Sampooranand Sanskrit University, Varanasi, first edition 2007, pp.32

² Dr, Agrawal Archana, Natya Shastriya Abhinay Siddhant avam Prayog, publisher Sampooranand Sanskrit University, Varanasi, first edition 2007, pp.18

³ Dr, Agrawal Archana, Natya Shastriya Abhinay Siddhant avam Prayog, publisher Sampooranand Sanskrit University, Varanasi, first edition 2007, pp.18

Propounded by Dr. Puru Dadhch ji, ‘Acting is the fine imitation that conveys the various artistic states and situations of the dramatic characters, which is a means of revealing the beauty or joyous elements of drama in front of the audience, that is, the means of feeling.’⁴

The purpose of acting is ultimately to provide rasa siddhi to the audience. In the Natyashastra tradition, after understanding the general form of acting, its four types have been explained, which have been named as Angik, Vachik, Aharya and Satvik. This has been accepted by all the later writers of Natyashastra, but in his Natya Lakshana Ratnakosh, Sagarnandi, has not called it Chaturvidha but has given the concept of Panchabhinaya (Vakya, Sucha, Ankur, Shaka , Nivrityanakur), which Bharat muni has enumerated under Samanayabhinav in Natya Shastra.

Keywords: Angik, Vachik, Aharya, Satvik, Samany Abhinay, Kathak, Abhinay, Rasa

"नाट्य शब्दों रसेमुख्यो, रसाभिव्यक्ति कारणम् चतुर्धाभिनयोपेतं लक्षणावृत्तितो बुधै॥"⁵

According to this verse of Sangeet Ratnakar, the reason for the expression of Rasa is that the dance consisting of four types of acting has been called Natya by the scholars. The feelings captured in poetry, which generate rasanbhuti in the audience, such feelings which are expressed by the dancer or acrobat are abhinay.

Angik (body) Abhinay:

The acting performed by various organs and appendages, which include physical, vocal and facial expressions, postures and movements and inflections and which express the feelings through charis, hand gestures, mandalas, angharas, karnas, is an Angik abhinaya. Bharat Muni has given a detailed description of the different functions of the body parts and their deployment in acting, which is very important for samanyabhinay. In this way, by using

⁴ Dr. Dadheech Puru, Ntya Prayog Ke Mool Tatva, Bindu Publication Manorama Ganj, Indore, 2021, pp. 73.

⁵ Aazad Pandit Teerathram, Kathak Gyaneshwari, Publication Nateshwar Kala Mandir Delhi, first edition 2008, pp.87

postures and gestures through body abhinay or body part appendages, Nat abhinaya works to achieve its goal by nourishing the ultimate goal and the essence of the drama.

Vachik (oral) Abhinay:

According to Bharat, Speech is the body of dance and drama. All oral acts in drama in the form of songs, arrangements etc. are oral acting. Speech that is language or whatever is heard and spoken in the world of language comes under verbal acting. Imitation of expression is essential in vocal acting. Under Vachik Abhinay, words, verses, signs, ornaments, qualities, defects, language and text style are represented. Verbal acting is based on language, in which rhythmicity is essential along with the use of words and figures of speech.

Aaharya Abhinay:

No play on stage is meaningful unless it includes costumes, makeup and other props. Therefore, Bharat has also considered Aaharya Abhinay as a capable element, which helps in taking the drama to the audience. Bharat has considered it as a decorative form of drama. This is the basis of acting. Imitation of external works plays an important role in bringing the character to life on stage. Aaharya means providing from outside. Mind, speech and actions are the living parts of the body of the Nut, its inner content, but the outer form is not a part of the body but is fed from outside, hence it is called Aaharya. Bharat considers it important for the success of the theatrical experiment.

Satvik (Virtuous) Abhinay:

This is the most important distinction of acting. Satva is the concentration of the mind. Satva arises when the mind is in the state of Samadhi. This virtue is called satvik abhinay in drama. That is, when the actor abandons his own nature with subtle expressions

and adopts the nature of the character and performs a sensitive act, then it is called Satvik abhinay.⁶

The origin of the word Satvik is "अवहितं मनः सत्वम तत्प्रयोजनं हेतुरस्येति सात्त्विक". This means, a focused mind is called Satva. The person whose purpose is being focused is called Satvik.⁷ Although it is an experience, because it is different from the essence, it has been considered separately. Bharat Muni has explained the Stambh, Swed, Romanch, Swar, Vepathu, Vevarnya, Ashru and Pralay etc. through the method of acting of Satvik bhavas. It is the subtle expression of emotions through Satvik experiences which are related to the emotions of a particular person which is called Satvik abhinay.

Bharat muni, after clarifying the Chaturvidha Abhinay in this way, in the 24th chapter of Natya Shastra, gave a deep and subtle thought about the balanced combination of these four acts and named it Samanyabhinay, That is, the name of proper mixing and use of these four acts on the stage. This is Samanyabhinay.

Samanya Abhinay

सामान्याभिनयो नाम ज्ञेयो वागंगसत्वजः(ना.शा.1/22)⁸

The combined acting of speech, organs and elements is known as samanyabhinay. The proportionate mixture of physical, verbal and Satvik abhinay is called samnyabhinay. Acting with graceful hand movements, soft body movements and sensuality is called general acting. Bharat Muni has written that general acting is accomplished by uniform use of head, hands, vision, waist, chest, thighs, karan etc. Satva has great importance in this. This essence remains latent in accumulated form. When this state of mind is displayed through speech,

⁶ Dr, Agrawal Archana, Natya Shastriya Abhinay Siddhant avam Prayog, publisher Sampooranand Sanskrit University, Varanasi, first edition 2007, pp.24

⁷ Dr. Dadheech Puru, Ntya Prayog Ke Mool Tatva, Bindu Publication Manorama Ganj, Indore, 2021, pp. 84.

⁸ Dr. Dadheech Puru, Ntya Prayog Ke Mool Tatva, Bindu Publication Manorama Ganj, Indore, 2021, pp. 85.

body movements through satvik feelings like thrill, tears etc. and gets the expression of rasa, then it is known as Samanyabhinaya.

According to Bharatmuni, in other words, these Satvik feelings are present in both men and women in the form of physical adornment. Which is called gesture- Hella. That is, there is a gradual development from Satva to Bhava, from Bhava to Hav and from Hav to Hella. When the feeling is ready to be expressed, the feeling of makeup starts appearing through the movement of the eyes, eyebrows and other body parts. The movement of the cervix causes the production of moans. When Srinagar, Rasa-dependent have the form of Lalita Abhinay i.e. Kamaniya form, then it is called Hella. There are three body parts of women, ten natural and seven Ayatnaja ornaments that are manifested from the body or organs which expand the feelings and emotions. In the context of samnyabhinay in Natya Shastra, only the acting description of affection feelings and states is mostly found, however, Bharat has tried to present it with decency, hence, under Bharat's general campaign, "equalization of actors, publication of virtuous feelings, very important topics like relation between essence and mind, sense meanings and results of actions and reactions of mind and soul, acting accordingly etc. have been discussed mainly in the context of amorousness, because in human life amorousness is more important than any other effort."⁹

Therefore, due to the predominance of Cheshta and the uniform use of all the acts by Bharat, it is completely meaningful to call it samnyabhinay. It is through these acting differences that the theatrical experiment is accomplished and the artist himself succeeds in taking his art to the heights of excellence through his means of expression and artistic work.

⁹ Dr. Dadheech Puru, Ntya Prayog Ke Mool Tatva, Bindu Publication Manorama Ganj, Indore, 2021, pp. 91.

To make the description clear, in Natya Shastra, Bharat Muni has divided the body parts used in samnyabhinay into Shariraj, Mukhaj and Cheshtakrit categories and has described the usefulness of their respective organs, appendages, pratyang etc. as important in samanyabhinay. Under which the purpose of Shiro Bheda, Drishti Bheda, Greeva Bheda, Bhru Karma, Tara Karma, Kapol, Chibuk etc. and details of their actions are explained. The minute analysis of the possible movements of these appendages given by Bharat Muni are important. According to Bharat, speech is a coordinated form of speech, body and essence is normal. For this, the author has explained the application of Sharirabhinay (Body Acting), Indriyaabhinay and Manobhaav (emotions) Abhinay.

Sharirabhinay (Body Acting)

Six types of Sharira Abhinay- Vakya, Sucha, Ankur, Shakha, Natyaayit and Nivrityankur are considered important for samanyabhinay.

1. **Vakya-** The Poetry in languages like Sanskrit, Prakrit etc. which is required for the expression of emotions and feelings is Vakya Abhinay or Vachik Abhinay.
2. **Soocha-** If the meaning of the sentence is first expressed through physical or virtuous actions and then the help of words is taken, Then it is called Soochabhinaya.
3. **Ankur-** Ankurabhinay is the use of one's imagination to make emotions effective through body movements. It includes body parts and speech.
4. **Shakha-** Bhav Abhinay performance comes through Shakha i.e. body parts, in which head, thigh, uru, pani, foot etc. are used. Use of arm movements is important in this.
5. **Dramatized (Natyayit)-** Displaying dance- based body movements in the pre-drama style comes under the category of Natyayiat, which includes Dhruvagana.

6. **Nivrutyanakur-** When other characters act out the words of another character, it is called Nivrutyanakur.

Indriyaabhinay:

In the Natya Shastra of Bharat Muni propounded by Dr. Brij Vallabh Mishra, where in the field of acting and dance, the method of operation of six body parts, six appendages etc. has been explained in the same experiment, there is a science even in the acting of the senses. In which Bharat Muni, while discussing the subtle expression of emotions, also discusses the senses because the mind is related to the senses. Bharat Muni Knows that in acting or dancing, when subtle emotions have to be expressed in the mind, the use of the five senses will be necessary, hence he has said-

शब्दं स्पर्शम् च रूपं च रसं गन्धं तथैव च
इन्द्रियाणीन्द्रियार्थाशयभावेरभनयेवदुधः¹⁰

Indriya Abhinay is to display the feelings of the mind through the five senses- sound, form, taste, smell and touch. To present an act related to the senses, it is essential to be mentally experienced. Unless the mind of the actor is experienced, he cannot act. Its application has been explained by Bharat Muni in this way.

1. **Shabda (sound)-** To enact the word through the sense of ear, the index finger is shown obliquely above the ear.
2. **Sparsh (touch)-** For this type of acting, eyes should be narrowed, expressions should be narrowed, forehead should be raised and should be kept touching the shoulders.
3. **Roop (Form)-** Enchanted expressions while keeping the Patak hastha on the head.

¹⁰ Datye Roshan, Kathak Aadi Kathak, Granthali Mudran, Dadar Mumbai, First edition 2010, pp. 22.

4. **Rasa/Gandh (taste/ smell)-** Taste and smell are the subject matter of the tongue and sense of smell, hence act with a happy voice by widening and narrowing the eyes while taking a deep breath.

Manobhāv (emotions) Abhinay:

Bharat Muni has described three parts of the mind for drama- Good, Bad and Intermediate. Happy singing, joy, thrill, cheerful mouth leads to favorable acting, sad mouth, narrowed eyes etc. lead to bad acting neither too happy nor too sad. If the middle emotions are described in this way, then it comes under intermediate emotional acting.

Expression Of Srinagar Rasa in Kathak Under Samanyabhinaya:

It could be understood that, for a Kathak artist, all these aspects related to acting described in Natya Shastra are necessary for normal acting because the acting aspect of Kathak dance is closer to naturalness as compared to other classical dances and it contains more elements of samanyabhinay . When seen from the perspective of Srinagar Rasa, Nayak Nayika bhed has an extraordinary place in the acting aspects of Kathak. The genres of tangibly express the concept of the Nayak-Nayika, i.e., Thumri, Kavitta, Pad, Gatbhaav, Bhajan, Hori, Chaiti, Kajri etc. the subtle aspects of abhinay to express the mood of the heroine, are done through samanyabhinay is being displayed only. The audience can feel the depth of the combination and separation of makeup and the unique style of expression through the spontaneous acting in Kathak. Kathak dancers bring the various mental states of the heroine to their peak through dance movements with natural emotions. Ms. Roshan Date writes in her book **Kathak- Aadi Kathak** that “Before any art form becomes visible, the artist has to go through a conceptual process. Imagination, Idea, Concept, Theory, Medium

and Style are those steps on the basis of which the artist reaches the pinnacle of his expressions.”¹¹

The ideals of female beauty that were established in ancient literature can be clearly seen in Kathak dance performances even today. For example, if we see the performance of Vasakasajja Nayika among the eight heroines specified by Bharat Muni, we can see her dressing up and waiting impatiently, the heroine eager to meet the hero, adorning her black thick hair with garlands of flowers and pearls. Remembering the embracing of the hero and becoming happy and getting excited, scenting the body with perfume, impatience of waiting in the eyes, etc., when kathak is performed on the stage, then it is accomplished only within the scope of classical beliefs and methods. The description of the heroine, makeup described in scriptures and literature and the makeup expressed in dance have a lot in common in terms of its presentation.

It is mentioned in Natya Shastra, ‘The Heroine, engrossed in the thoughts and contemplation of the hero, should look with a half – hearted gaze, display feminine gestures by touching the bracelet, bangles or the girdle in her hands, and the hero should inhale repeatedly. Express the worry that is plaguing your mind because someone is not coming’.¹²

All the feelings mentioned above have been expressed in the Thumri presented by Kathak artist Ranjana Phadke ji in the form of Vasakasajja Nayika, whose illustrations are presented below:

गूँध लावो री मालनिया, बेगी हरवा करहुं सिंगरवा

डारु गरवा, हंस हंस पिया को मनावूं

गावो मंगलचार, बधावो नित उठ करु काज

¹¹ Datye Roshan, Kathak Aadi Kathak, Granthali Mudran, Dadar Mumbai, First edition 2010, Page 139

¹² Datye Roshan, Kathak Aadi Kathak, Granthali Mudran, Dadar Mumbai, First edition 2010, Page 143

गूँध लावो री मालनिया

लगन मोरी लाग रही सजनी रजनी

उन बिन कैसे सहे अब घडी घडी पल पल छिन छिन

निस दिन यही काज, गूँध लावो री मालनिया¹³

Vasaksajja Nayika:

नायक के इंतज़ार में बाट जोहती नायिका

अपने बालों को सवारती हुई नायिका

नायक के साथ आलिंगन के क्षणों को याद कर

अर्धोन्मिलित दृष्टि से चिंतन मे निमग्न नायिका

¹³ Phadke Ranjana, Society for Indian Music and Art. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uSkOGSeYyVw>.

In Kathak dance, to express the Vasakasajja Nayika in conjunction with the make-up, such various expressions are demonstrated by Samanyabhinaya.

Similarly, the communicative expressions have their own important contribution in showing the detached form of makeup. In which the emotional display of the heroine Khandita is very important. The feelings of jealousy, reproach, anger, sorrow, jealousy, hatred, respect, insult, tears, joy etc. which are transmitted in the heroine's mind after spending the night with another woman and seeing the signs of Rati Janya Kriya. When a Kathak artist expresses it on the stage, it comes under the category of samnyabhinay because it is Satvik Angabhinay which keeps the theatrical tradition alive by expressing the personality of the heroine in an attractive and lively form. To master this type of acting, not only practice is required but also emotional experience, which can arouse emotions in the audience and make them feel emotional. Therefore, the importance of communicative or adulterous expressions is considered very important for acting.

Photographs of the communication expressions of the Khandita Nayika performed by Guru Dr. Vibha Dadheech ji are presented here which explain it,

The smile of the heroine happy with the arrival of her beloved, with a humorous glance, the frown, the way the eyes move here and there, in the next moment becomes stable.

The Heroine's tearful eyes filled with the emotions of sorrow, jealousy, pride, insult etc., with her eyelids bowed down with pity after seeing the signs of intimacy with another woman.

The following poses seem appropriate considering the anger of the heroine and her rebuke to the hero,

पलकन पीक अधर में में अंजन, कहो पिया तुम कहाँ लगाएं
अखियन में मद छलकी रह्यो, अरु लटपट पैर घने छबि छाए
सोहे खाइए न बात बनाईये, न मानूंगी मैं पिय लाख मनाएँ
क्यों पग पाग धरो मेरे पिय, जाओ वहीं जहाँ रैन बिताएँ¹⁴

¹⁴ Dr. Dev Manjari, Kathak nritya me Kavitta Chhand, India Printing work Vadala Mumbai, II edition 2019, pp.194

Srinagar has always been a special part of Kathak dance performance. In the context of inducing rasa, the beautified performance of the woman in the sringar based dance holds special significance. The four types of acts of samnyabhinay described by Bharat Muni, Aangik, Vachik, Aharya and Satvik, have all been performed in decorated artistic performances. In this decorative presentation of Kathak dance, some special hastaks and sthanaks are also used which, despite being from the scriptures, are based on folk traditions. In the presentation of Nayika Bhed Abhinay in Kathak dance, Vasakasajja Naika is presented in Gaat Bhava and Thumri, which is performed keeping in mind the elements of samanyaabhinay along with all the experiences. The experiences of the heroine described in Natyashastra have been interpreted in Kathak with the use of Drishti Bheda, Greeva Bheda, Hasta Mudra, Upaveshna etc. In this way, many examples can be seen in the Kathak performances, expressing the feelings of joy and sadness in the mutual relationship of the hero and the heroine, mental states, hopes, disappointments, mania etc., this gross, subtle and deficiencies of makeup can be seen.

Conclusion:

In this way, the method of samanyabhinay suggested by Bharat to make this Sanskrit theatrical classical tradition alive and attractive for high quality acting, over time, despite changes in its form along with local elements, developed as a specialty of a particular place. We can also accept the proper meaning of the word Panchangabhinaya mentioned in Malvikagnimitram by Kalidas as the management of acting described in Natya Shastra as Panchangabhinaya i.e. Vakya, Shakha, Ankur, Sucha, Natya and Nivrityankur etc. In this way, after mastering the four broad types of acting described in the Natya shastra, Bharat

Muni, in the 24th chapter, has enunciated the essential and metaphorical types of body acting under the samnyabhinay and has propounded its importance.¹⁵

Due to the predominance of kamasutra in worldly life, Bharat Muni must have considered the origin of all bhava from it. Therefore, in the context of samanyabhinay in Natya Shastra, there is mostly description of acting of sensuous emotions and states, but it talks about experimenting with decency. In this way, the work of conveying the sentence and its meaning to the audience is done by the dancer by making the meaning of the verse more effective through various processes and reaction of Satvik feelings through acting. These methods established by Bharat Muni are still used somewhere or the other. Although the classical theatrical methods of organic acting are not present at one place today, they are still present in classical dance in many forms. In this way, due to the predominance of movement, equality of all the acts is visible in the common act, which gives it significance. It is through these acting differences that the theatrical experiment is accomplished. Srinagar has always been a special part of Kathak dance performance. Depth of expression achieved through subtle actions of various body parts. This innate tendency of adornment is eternal. The expression of the heroine described in Natya Shastra through acting in different centuries is a witness to the intact tradition of literature and art.

References:

1. Dr, Agrawal Archana, Natya Shastriya Abhinay Siddhant avam Prayog, publisher Sampooranand Sanskrit University, Varanasi, first edition 2007
2. Dr. Dadheech Puru, Ntya Prayog Ke Mool Tatva, Bindu Publication Manorama Ganj, Indore, 2021.
3. Datye Roshan, Kathak Aadi Kathak, Granthali Mudran, Dadar Mumbai, First edition 2010.
4. Dr. Dev Manjari, Kathak nritya me Kavitta Chhand, India Printing work Vadala Mumbai, II edition 2019.
5. Dr. Dadheech Puru, Dr. Dadheech Vibha, Nritya nibandh, Bindu Publication, Manorama Gang, Indore, First edition 2009.

¹⁵ Dr. Dadheech Puru, Dr. Dadheech Vibha, Nritya nibandh, Bindu Publication, Manorama Gang, Indore, First edition 2009. pp. 245.
